

Irish Research eLibrary

National Open Access Monitor Survey: Organisational Identity: New Submissions

IMPORTANT

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The first iteration of this survey was originally run during October 2023.

If your organisation has already submitted to that survey, **DO NOT COMPLETE THIS SURVEY AGAIN.**

Only complete this form if this is the first time your organisation will be submitting a survey response.

If you would like to update an existing submission, please complete a change file submission here: [\[link\]](#).

Any submission from an organisation that has already submitted will not be actioned.

If you would like to check if your organisation has already submitted, please check here: [\[download link\]](#)

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Introduction

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Introduction

This survey is carried out under the National Open Access Monitoring project, funded by Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the NORF Open Research Fund 2022 to address one of the six priority actions of Ireland's [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2023](#).

This survey is for Research Performing Organisations, Research Funding Organisations and Publisher stakeholders of the National Open Access Monitor.

The purpose of this survey is to empower stakeholders to self-identify how their entities will be represented in the National Open Access Monitor.

The survey expects one response from each stakeholder entity. If multiple responses are obtained and inconsistencies occur, the Project Manager will follow up directly with respondents to clarify. To view a reference PDF of this survey, please click here [\[link\]](#).

Throughout this survey:

- The National Open Access Monitor, Ireland will be referred to as the Monitor.
- Research Performing Organisations will be referred to as RPOs and Research Funding Organisation will be referred to as RFOs.
- Persistent Identifiers will be referred to as PIDs.

The sections of this survey are:

1. Consent
2. Survey Respondent Identification
3. Potential Survey Skip Point [for Publishers]
4. RPO and RFO Dashboards
5. RPO and RFO Identification
6. RPO and RFO Categorisation
7. Publicly Funded Organisations/Entities
8. Affiliated Organisations/Entities
9. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): RPOs and RFOs Publisher Branching [end survey for non-Publishers]
10. RPO/RFO Publisher Identification
11. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): RPO/RFO Publishers
12. Publisher Identification
13. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): Publishers
14. Optional: RPO Identity Supplement
15. Submit Survey

There is no deadline for responses to this survey.

Please note: all survey data will be retained and hosted on a third party (Online Surveys) server and not on a MU server. For more information on how and why this survey data is being collected, and how it will be managed, please refer to the [Stakeholder Information Sheet and Consent Form](#).

Your submission may be paused at any time by pressing "Finish Later". Respondents who click on the "Finish Later" link are taken to a page giving the survey's closing date and a 'finish later' URL. This URL can be used to return to the survey at the page on which you clicked the 'Finish later' link. The URL can be either bookmarked in your browser, or you will be asked if you would like the URL to be emailed to you.

A download of your responses will be available to you on completion.

If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and/or to withdraw your information up until such time as the contributions are actioned upon for the development of the National Open Access Monitor. The deadline to withdraw a submission from this form is COB the Thursday after your submission (in the case of Thursday submissions, the deadline is COB that same day).

If you have any questions relating to this survey, or require assistance in filling it out, please contact Dr Catherine Ferris (National Open Access Monitor Project Manager): catherine.ferris@mu.ie

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Consent

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Formal contributors to the National Open Access Monitor Project (e.g. through stakeholder surveys like this) are required to complete and return a consent form **in advance of contributing**. This is a requirement of the Maynooth University Research Ethics Procedure.

If you have not yet completed a consent form:

1. stop here
2. complete the consent form, available at [this link](#)
3. return it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie
4. and then return to this survey.

Important: if the date/time of the survey response precedes the date/time that the consent form is received, the survey response will be **immediately deleted**.

If you have completed the consent form (an image of the first page is below as a reminder), please select yes below and continue.

Purpose of the Study. I am Dr Catherine Ferris, [JReL](#) Open Scholarship Officer (Maynooth University) and Project Manager of the National Open Access Monitor Project, funded by the National Open Research Forum.

This project will develop a monitor for open access at the national level, initially through pilot reports and a national dashboard to publish, analyse and track progress towards 100% open access. The key objectives and expected outcomes are to:

- Work to arrive at a community-agreed definition for Open Access at the national level
- Build on previous NORF work, engaging with national stakeholders (DFHERIS, NORF, NORF 2022 Open Research Fund projects, HEA, research funding organisation, research performing organisations, national research infrastructures, publishers etc.) to gather and validate user requirements for Open Access monitoring
- Work with external vendors to deliver reports and a national dashboard to help Ireland publish, analyse and track open access rates at the national level.
- Document challenges that should be addressed in long-term monitoring solutions and recommend steps to be taken, including workflows for data validation and enrichment.
- Work to improve the quality and depth of data used for the national dashboard in line with international best practice through stakeholder collaboration with institutions, funders etc. and direct input or validation where possible.
- Following NORF and Science Europe recommendations, ensure that the monitor uses data and bibliographic databases that are openly accessible, is built using open infrastructure, and is publicly accessible to view and analyse.

A copy of the Project Plan is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7331432>

What will the study involve and what information will be collected?

Participants will be asked to provide input and contribute as representatives of stakeholder entities, over the course of the two-year project (1 November 2022-1 November 2024), in the following areas:

- to arrive at a community-agreed definition for Open Access in this context at the national level
- to validate, and if required expand on, the user stories and functional requirements of the National Open Access Monitor identified by the NORF OA Monitoring Policy Brief Group. These functional requirements should explicitly state current OA reporting metrics for each stakeholder, required data points and potential future requirements.
- to monitor and track the costs associated with contributing to this project and to provide this data to the Project Manager, for inclusion in the final report to the funder, in a pseudonymised format (to the high-level stakeholder group) to demonstrate the cost of this work to the national research system.
- to provide metadata and persistent identifiers as required, to enable the successful delivery of the pilot dashboard
- to provide feedback on the pilot dashboard
- if necessary, to work with the Project Manager to determine the impact of vendor non-deliverables
- to work with the Project Manager to identify gaps, incomplete representation, or errors in pilot data.
- to work to improve the quality and depth of data used for the national dashboard.

1. Have you completed the National Open Access Monitor Project Stakeholder Consent Form, and returned it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie? *

Yes

No

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Consent Disclaimer

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The National Open Access Monitor Project Stakeholder Consent Form allows participants to choose to be pseudonymised, if you would rather your contribution was not publicly attributed to you and your organisation/entity.

However, due to the nature and purpose of this survey on Organisational Identity, the **identity of your organisation/entity cannot be pseudonymised**. Therefore, while your name will remain pseudonymised, it will be evident that a representative of your organisation/entity contributed to this survey.

- If you chose pseudonymisation in the consent form, and are happy to continue with this survey under these conditions, please continue.
- If you chose pseudonymisation in the consent form, and are **not** happy to continue with this survey under these conditions, please stop here and forward this survey onto another person in your organisation/entity to complete.

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Survey Respondent Identification

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2. Your name *

3. Your department *

4. Your job title *

5. Your email address (the Project Manager may need to follow-up with you on your responses. Your email address will not be made public.) *

6. The name of the organisation/entity that you represent *

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Potential Survey Skip Point

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7. Questions 8-30 are applicable for RPOs and RFOs only, and are not applicable to Publishers. If your organisation/entity is a Publisher (and not also an RPO/RFO), then please indicate below and the survey will skip directly to the Publisher Persistent Identifier section of the survey *

- My organisation/entity is a Publisher
- My organisation/entity is an RPO; an RFO; an RPO & RFO; an RPO & Publisher; an RFO & Publisher; or an RPO, RFO & Publisher

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RPO and RFO Dashboards

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The National Open Access Monitor will include dashboards for each RPO and RFO. The dashboards will be automatically created for all Irish organisations/entities represented in the OpenAIRE Graph metadata: <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/entities/organization>.

A presentation slide titled 'RPO & RFO Dashboards' with a slide number '13' in a blue box. The slide lists four main features: 'Comprehensive insights into each Irish RPO's and RFO's activities and OS performance', 'Indicators View' (with sub-points for OA uptake and breakdowns), 'Research Outputs View' (with sub-points for browsing and searching), and 'RPO/RFO Managers' (with sub-points for Sandbox and OpenORGS access). The OpenAIRE logo is in the bottom left, and the footer text reads 'National Open Access Monitor, Ireland [1st Stakeholder Webinar] 22 September 2023'.

The questions in this section are to:

- ensure we have a complete list of Irish RPOs and RFOs
- ensure that we can identify organisations/entities missing from the OpenAIRE Graph metadata
- ensure each organisation/entity is categorised correctly as RPO or RFO as applicable.

In the next section, please select the organisation/entity you represent, and indicate if it is an RPO, an RFO, both an RFO and RPO, or neither.

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RPO and RFO Identification

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8. Select the name of the organisation/entity you represent (listed in alphabetical order) *

- ADAPT - Centre for Digital Content Technology
- AMBER - Advanced Materials and BioEngineering Research
- APC - Microbiome Institute
- APT – Advanced Processing Technology Research Centre Dublin
- Atlantic Technological University
- BiOrbic Bioeconomy Research Centre
- Bord Iascaigh Mhara
- CAPP - Centre for Advanced Photonics and Process Analysis
- CCT Dublin
- CeADAR – Data Analytics & Machine Intelligence
- Central Bank & Financial Services Authority of Ireland
- Centre for Veterinary Epidemiological Research Analysis
- COMAND - Interactive Media Technologies
- CONFIRM - Smart Manufacturing Research Centre
- CONNECT - The Centre for Future Networks and Communications
- CREDIT - Centre for Renewables and Energy
- CREST - Centre for Research in Engineering Surface Technology
- CÚRAM SFI Research Centre for Medical Devices
- Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine
- Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth

- Department of Education
- Department of Enterprise, Trade and Employment
- Department of Foreign Affairs
- Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science
- Department of Health
- Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage
- Department of Public Expenditure and Reform
- Department of Rural and Community Development
- Department of Social Protection
- Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications
- Department of the Taoiseach
- Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media
- Department of Transport
- Design+ Applied Design Technology Gateway
- Dorset College
- Dublin Business School
- Dublin City University
- Dublin Dental University Hospital
- Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies
- Dun Laoghaire Institute of Art, Design & Technology
- Dundalk Institute of Technology
- Economic and Social Research Institute
- Educational Research Centre
- Enterprise Ireland
- Environmental Protection Agency
- Ervia & Gas Networks Ireland
- Fáilte Ireland
- Food for Health Ireland - Dublin
- FutureNeuro - Centre for Chronic and Rare Neurological Diseases
- Galway Business School
- Geological Survey Ireland
- Griffith College
- Health Information and Quality Authority
- Health Research Board
- Health Research Charities Ireland
- Health Service Executive
- Heritage Council
- Hibernia College
- Higher Education Authority
- Holmes Institute Dublin
- Houses of the Oireachtas
- Housing Agency

- Ibat College
- ICD Business School
- iCRAG - Irish Centre for Research in Applied Geosciences
- IDA Ireland
- I-Form Advanced Manufacturing Research Centre - Dublin
- IMaR - Intelligent Mechatronics and RFID
- IMR - Irish Manufacturing Research
- Independent College Dublin
- INFANT - Irish Centre for Foetal and Neonatal Translational
- Inland Fisheries Ireland
- Insight – Centre for Data Analytics
- Institute of Public Health in Ireland
- InterTradeIreland
- IPIC - Irish Photonic Integration Centre
- IReL
- Irish Aid
- Irish Cancer Society
- Irish College of General Practitioners
- Irish Fulbright Commission
- Irish Research Council
- Learnovate Centre
- Lero - The Science Foundation Ireland Research Centre for Software
- Low Pay Commission
- MaREI - Marine Renewable Energy Ireland
- Marine Institute
- Marino Institute of Education
- Mary Immaculate College
- Maynooth University
- MCCI - Microelectronics
- Met Éireann
- MET Gateway - Medical & Engineering Technology
- MiCRA - Microsensors for Clinical Research and Analysis
- MTI - Meat Technology Ireland
- Munster Technological University
- National Cancer Registry Ireland
- National College of Art & Design
- National College of Ireland
- National Disability Authority
- National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education
- National Monuments Service
- National Standards Authority of Ireland
- National Suicide Research Foundation

- NIBRT - National Institute for Bioprocessing Research & Training
- NIMBUS - Embedded Computing and Software Systems
- National Open Research Forum
- Office of Public Works
- Office of the Planning Regulator
- Pharmaceutical Manufacturing (PMTc)
- PMBrc - Pharmaceutical & Molecular Biotechnology
- Precision Engineering, Materials and Manufacturing research
- PRISM - Polymer, Recycling, Industrial, Sustainability and Manufacturing Research Institute
- Royal College of Physicians Ireland
- Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland
- Royal Irish Academy of Music
- Science Foundation Ireland
- SEAM - South Eastern Applied Materials Research Centre
- Shannon ABC - Nutraceuticals Research
- SOLAS
- South-East Technological University
- Sport Ireland
- SSPC, the SFI Research Centre for Pharmaceuticals
- St John of Gods Research Foundation
- Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
- Teagasc
- Technological University Dublin
- Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest
- The Arts Council
- The Dairy Processing Technology Centre
- The Irish Centre for High-End Computing
- The Open Training College
- Transport Infrastructure Ireland
- Trinity College Dublin
- Tusla
- Tyndall National Institute
- Údarás na Gaeltachta
- Uisce Éireann
- University College Cork
- University College Dublin
- University of Galway
- University of Limerick
- VistaMilk
- Walton Institute
- Waterways Ireland
- WiSAR Lab - Wireless Sensor Technologies

Other

9. If your organisation/entity was not listed, or your organisation/entity was listed but not referred to correctly, please provide the name of your organisation/entity here

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RPO and RFO Categorisation

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10. Please indicate if your organisation/entity is an RPO, an RFO, both an RFO and RPO, or neither. *

- RPO
- RFO
- RPO and RFO
- neither RPO nor RFO

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Publicly Funded Organisations/Entities

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As per the tender requirements, the Monitor must identify publicly funded research outputs.

Item	Requirement	Mandatory / Desirable
B1	The Monitor MUST show to what extent Irish scholarly publications resulting from publicly funded research are immediately openly available by default and are accessible on an ongoing basis. Publicly funded in this context is defined as "Publicly funded research is research undertaken in whole or in part via publicly funded resourcing or remuneration, e.g., salaries, grants, contracts, etc."	M

Publicly funded, in this context, has been defined in the [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030](#).

²⁰ Publicly funded research is research undertaken in whole or in part via publicly funded resourcing or remuneration, e.g. salaries, grants, contracts, etc.

Therefore, it is expected that the following will be identified as "publicly funded" research outputs in the Monitor:

- Irish scholarly publications by staff of organisations/entities which are partially or fully publicly funded;

- and Irish scholarly publications, partially or fully funded by publicly-funded Irish funders.

In the next question, please identify if your organisation/entity is in receipt of public funding.

11. Is your organisation/entity in receipt of public funding? To note: if your organisation/entity is partially funded by public funding and partially funded by other means, select yes. *

yes

no

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Affiliated Organisations/Entities

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[To note: this text has been updated from the live survey of October 2023 based on feedback]

It is acknowledged that many research organisations/entities in Ireland are formally affiliated, either as parent/child entities under a parent legal entity, or due to formal research agreements which mean that research outputs from Entity A should also be attributed to Entity B. It is expected that in the Monitor, these relationships will be reflected in the following way: the research outputs of Entity A will appear on the dashboard of Entity A and also on the dashboard of Entity B. **Your input is needed here**, as the experts in the complex legal relationships your organisation/entities has, to define the appropriate representation of those organisations' research outputs in the Monitor.

For this question, you are asked to specify the name of another organisation/entity where either:

(a) all the research outputs of that organisation/entity should appear on their dashboard, and also on your organisation/entity's dashboard; or

(b) all the research outputs of your organisation/entity should appear on your own dashboard, but also on the dashboard of the other organisation/entity.

Important:

1. This survey expects responses from **each entity** in the relationship. **Only where all entities agree there is a formal relationship in place** that should be reflected in the Monitor will the link be implemented. To enable this

verification process, please forward this survey to the relevant staff within the other entities for them to complete.

2. This section of the survey is to represent relationships of RPO-to-RPO and RFO-to-RFO, but not RPO-to-RFO. Research outputs of an RPO funded by an RFO will appear in both dashboards automatically (metadata dependent).
3. This section of the survey is not intended to capture the multiple affiliations of individual researchers associated with your organisation/entity. If an individual researcher is affiliated with HEI 4 and HEI 40, their research outputs will appear in both HEI dashboard 4 and HEI dashboard 40 automatically (metadata dependent). It is also not intended to capture data on scenarios where e.g. a research centre is affiliated with multiple higher education institutions.
4. Affiliated organisations/entities for this question may include research centres, hospitals etc, but not departments.

12. Please indicate (as per the description above): *

- My organisation/entity is formally affiliated with another organisation/entity
- My organisation/entity is not formally affiliated with another organisation/entity

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Affiliated Organisations/Entities (Part 2)

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13. Please select the other organisation(s) and/or entities that your organisation/entity is formally affiliated to, as per the definition listed on the previous page (listed in alphabetical order) To note: do not enter your organisation here, you've already selected your organisation in Question 8. *

- ADAPT - Centre for Digital Content Technology
- AMBER - Advanced Materials and BioEngineering Research
- APC - Microbiome Institute
- APT – Advanced Processing Technology Research Centre Dublin
- Atlantic Technological University
- BiOrbic Bioeconomy Research Centre
- Bord Iascaigh Mhara
- CAPP - Centre for Advanced Photonics and Process Analysis
- CCT Dublin
- CeADAR – Data Analytics & Machine Intelligence
- Central Bank & Financial Services Authority of Ireland
- Centre for Veterinary Epidemiological Research Analysis
- COMAND - Interactive Media Technologies
- CONFIRM - Smart Manufacturing Research Centre
- CONNECT - The Centre for Future Networks and Communications
- CREDIT - Centre for Renewables and Energy
- CREST - Centre for Research in Engineering Surface Technology
- CÚRAM SFI Research Centre for Medical Devices

- Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine
- Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth
- Department of Education
- Department of Enterprise, Trade and Employment
- Department of Foreign Affairs
- Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science
- Department of Health
- Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage
- Department of Public Expenditure and Reform
- Department of Rural and Community Development
- Department of Social Protection
- Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications
- Department of the Taoiseach
- Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media
- Department of Transport
- Design+ Applied Design Technology Gateway
- Dorset College
- Dublin Business School
- Dublin City University
- Dublin Dental University Hospital
- Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies
- Dun Laoghaire Institute of Art, Design & Technology
- Dundalk Institute of Technology
- Economic and Social Research Institute
- Educational Research Centre
- Enterprise Ireland
- Environmental Protection Agency
- Ervia & Gas Networks Ireland
- Fáilte Ireland
- Food for Health Ireland - Dublin
- FutureNeuro - Centre for Chronic and Rare Neurological Diseases
- Galway Business School
- Geological Survey Ireland
- Griffith College
- Health Information and Quality Authority
- Health Research Board
- Health Research Charities Ireland
- Health Service Executive
- Heritage Council
- Hibernia College
- Higher Education Authority
- Holmes Institute Dublin

- Houses of the Oireachtas
- Housing Agency
- Ibat College
- ICD Business School
- iCRAG - Irish Centre for Research in Applied Geosciences
- IDA Ireland
- I-Form Advanced Manufacturing Research Centre - Dublin
- IMaR - Intelligent Mechatronics and RFID
- IMR - Irish Manufacturing Research
- Independent College Dublin
- INFANT - Irish Centre for Foetal and Neonatal Translational
- Inland Fisheries Ireland
- Insight – Centre for Data Analytics
- Institute of Public Health in Ireland
- InterTradelreland
- IPIC - Irish Photonic Integration Centre
- IReL
- Irish Aid
- Irish Cancer Society
- Irish College of General Practitioners
- Irish Fulbright Commission
- Irish Research Council
- Learnovate Centre
- Lero - The Science Foundation Ireland Research Centre for Software
- Low Pay Commission
- MaREI - Marine Renewable Energy Ireland
- Marine Institute
- Marino Institute of Education
- Mary Immaculate College
- Maynooth University
- MCCI - Microelectronics
- Met Éireann
- MET Gateway - Medical & Engineering Technology
- MiCRA - Microsensors for Clinical Research and Analysis
- MTI - Meat Technology Ireland
- Munster Technological University
- National Cancer Registry Ireland
- National College of Art & Design
- National College of Ireland
- National Disability Authority
- National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education
- National Monuments Service

- National Standards Authority of Ireland
- National Suicide Research Foundation
- NIBRT - National Institute for Bioprocessing Research & Training
- NIMBUS - Embedded Computing and Software Systems
- National Open Research Forum
- Office of Public Works
- Office of the Planning Regulator
- Pharmaceutical Manufacturing (PMTc)
- PMBrc - Pharmaceutical & Molecular Biotechnology
- Precision Engineering, Materials and Manufacturing research
- PRISM - Polymer, Recycling, Industrial, Sustainability and Manufacturing Research Institute
- Royal College of Physicians Ireland
- Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland
- Royal Irish Academy of Music
- Science Foundation Ireland
- SEAM - South Eastern Applied Materials Research Centre
- Shannon ABC - Nutraceuticals Research
- SOLAS
- South-East Technological University
- Sport Ireland
- SSPC, the SFI Research Centre for Pharmaceuticals
- St John of Gods Research Foundation
- Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
- Teagasc
- Technological University Dublin
- Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest
- The Arts Council
- The Dairy Processing Technology Centre
- The Irish Centre for High-End Computing
- The Open Training College
- Transport Infrastructure Ireland
- Trinity College Dublin
- Tusla
- Tyndall National Institute
- Údarás na Gaeltachta
- Uisce Éireann
- University College Cork
- University College Dublin
- University of Galway
- University of Limerick
- VistaMilk
- Walton Institute

- Waterways Ireland
- WiSAR Lab - Wireless Sensor Technologies
- Other

14. If the affiliated organisation(s) and or entities are not listed here, please provide a list of the full names of those organisations/entities, separated by semicolons (no spaces):

15. Please indicate: *

- I expect the research outputs of the selected organisation(s)/entities to appear in my organisation's/entity's dashboard
- I expect the research outputs of my organisation/entity to appear in the selected organisation(s)/entities' dashboard(s)
- Both

If you selected Both:

16. For "I expect the research outputs of the selected organisation(s)/entities to appear in my organisation's/entity's dashboard", please list the selected organisation(s)/entities this applies to

17. For "I expect the research outputs of my organisation/entity to appear in the selected organisation(s)/entities' dashboard(s)", please list the selected organisation(s)/entities this applies to

18. Please indicate if, to the best of your knowledge, your organisation/entity is one entity in a many-to-many affiliation relationship, as this will require additional analysis to ensure that research outputs are attributed to the correct RPOs.

- yes
- no
- don't know

19. If your organisation/entity is formally affiliated with another organisation/entity, and that relationship is not captured in the survey questions above, please provide details here, and give your expectation for how affected research outputs should be represented in the Monitor dashboards

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Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): RPOs and RFOs

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The [tender](#) requirements for the Monitor specified that the vendor must (at a minimum) use PIDs to identify Irish scholarly publications:

M6	The Monitor MUST , at a minimum:	Compliant (Yes / No)	Insert Comment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Use the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of "open access": "By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself." https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read/Use the Unpaywall definition of "open access types".Initially focus on monitoring peer-reviewed articles and conference proceedingsHave the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during Action 6.2.3, expected in 2025-2027)Focus on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI.Define an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata.		

The Monitor will be built using open data from the OpenAIRE Graph:

DATA BACKBONE: THE OPENAIRE GRAPH

- **A Scientific Knowledge Graph**
 - Timely and comprehensive coverage of research outputs
 - 129K data sources, 3M projects, and 235M research outputs (publications, software, datasets, other research products)
 - Near monthly updates
- **Precision, depth & processing**
 - Rigorous cleaning, deduplication, and enrichment for optimal accuracy
 - Enriched metadata links: Research results to projects, author affiliations, and classifications (FoS, SDG)
 - Techniques for duplicate identification in addition to OpenAIRE's curation tools
- **Robustness & openness**
 - Maintenance, load balancing, backups, overseen by the OpenAIRE technology centre
 - Open data & transparent methodologies

This section is to capture the PIDs that represent RPOs and RFOs that will be represented in the Monitor, to enable OpenAIRE to query the OpenAIRE graph using those PIDs and identify research outputs associated with your organisation/entity.

Please supply the most comprehensive listing of identifiers that you have available to you. When providing lists, please provide the PIDs separated by semicolons (no spaces) (e.g. 8798;8849)

If your organisation is one organisation/entity in a one-to-one, one-to-many, or many-to-many relationship, please only supply the PIDs that identify your discreet RPO/RFO organisation/entity. To enable a comprehensive collation of relevant PIDs for this process, **please forward this survey to the relevant staff within the other affiliated organisations/entities** for them to complete their PID submission.

20. ROR

<https://ror.org/>

21. RINGGOLD

<https://www.copyright.com/solutions-ringgold/guest-users/>

22. GRID

https://digitalscience.figshare.com/articles/dataset/GRID_release_2021-09-16/16685428?backTo=/collections/GRID/3812929

23. ISNI

<https://isni.oclc.org/cbs/>

24. For RFOs only: Open Funder Registry (previously known as the Crossref Funder Registry, or FundRef)

<https://doi.crossref.org/funderNames?mode=list>

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Publisher Branching

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25. Please identify the following: *

- My RPO/RFO is also a Publisher
- My RPO/RFO is not also a Publisher

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RPO/RFO Publisher Identification

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26. If the name of your Publisher organisation/entity is different to the name of your RPO/RFO organisation/entity, please indicate the full name of your Publisher organisation/entity, to be associated with the persistent identifiers that you will provide in the next section

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Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): RPO/RFO Publishers

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Please supply the most comprehensive listing of identifiers that you have available to you. When providing lists, please provide the PIDs separated by semicolons (no spaces) (e.g. 8798;8849) If your Publisher organisation is part of another organisation/entity, please only supply the PIDs that identify your discreet Publisher organisation/entity.

27. ROR

<https://ror.org/>

28. RINGGOLD

<https://www.copyright.com/solutions-ringgold/guest-users/>

29. GRID

https://digitalscience.figshare.com/articles/dataset/GRID_release_2021-09-16/16685428?backTo=/collections/GRID/3812929

30. ISNI

<https://isni.oclc.org/cbs/>

31. ISSNs

<https://portal.issn.org/>

32. e-ISSNs

<https://portal.issn.org/>

33. ISSN-L

<https://portal.issn.org/>

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34. Please select Continue to move to the next section *

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Optional: RPO Identity Supplement

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OpenAIRE provide the option for RPOs to enhance the representation of their organisation/entity by supplementing the OpenAIRE Graph metadata with data from their organisation's/entity's CRIS and/or Institutional Repositories.

The image shows a screenshot of the 'Repository Dashboard' interface. On the left, a vertical red bar contains the text 'Repository Dashboard' and the OpenAIRE logo. The main content area lists features and benefits for repositories registered in OpenAIRE. A blue box with the number '20' is in the top right corner. The interface includes a list of metrics and indicators, a section for 'Full Functionality for Repositories registered in OpenAIRE', and a list of optional actions like 'Register, validate (including FAIRness checks), and enrich records (via OpenAIRE BROKER)'. On the right, there are several overlapping screenshots of the dashboard's data visualization components, including a table with numerical data and various charts.

If your RPO would like to participate in this optional action, please provide the name, system name and URL of your Institutional Repository and/or CRIS (as applicable) next.

Providing this information does not obligate your organisation/entity to register your system with OpenAIRE as part of the Monitor project. This information is being captured at this point to assist OpenAIRE in identifying existing and potential integration points for this optional enhancement activity.

Please skip this question if not applicable.

44. Institutional Repository Name

45. Institutional Repository System Name

46. Institutional Repository URL

47. CRIS Name

48. CRIS System Name

49. CRIS URL

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Please click submit below to complete the survey

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